

Everyday mindfulness for the academic workplace

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Purpose

The aim of the proposed workshop is two-fold. It is intended to offer an overview of the most updated research findings on mindfulness (also referred to as mind-body connection) and to introduce short hands-on practices that researchers may apply in a day-to-day setting, in or outside the workplace.

Literature support for mindfulness

There is increasing research evidence for the benefits of mindfulness in promoting emotional health and preventing burnout in the workplace (see Allen et al., 2015; Hülshager et al., 2013 for a review). Awareness of emotion, including the bodily sensations and thoughts associated with it, is the first step to emotion regulation (Hoemann et al., 2019). There is evidence that it can be trained, and it can be conceived as developing a habit or ‘muscle’ of the mind-body connection (Hoemann, Barrett and Quigley, 2021). The ability to identify and name emotional experience and the associated bodily reactions, known as emotional granularity or differentiation, has been shown to be linked to less anxiety (Kashdan, Barrett and McKnight, 2015).

Principal design

While there are many types of mindfulness practices of various durations, the workshop includes those kinds that are suitable for beginners and may be done in a short time and virtually anywhere. The idea is to make it as implementable and motivating for participants.

Although mindfulness has historical links to some religions, this workshop draws on secular and science-informed mindfulness practice.

Proposed flow of the workshop

1. Introducing mindfulness and the most updated research (neuroscience and psychology); what mindfulness is, what it may help with and what it may not do (words of caution)
2. Sharing experience practicing and teaching mindfulness: anecdotal evidence
3. Participants engaging in hands-on practices guided by the workshop host-
 - a) Warm-up/Prelude: Observing and allowing the mind to wander (non-judgement), softening into greater awareness of the body
 - b) Breathing
 - c) Slow hand movement

Depending on the time allowed, a practice on emotional differentiation (i.e., describing how one feels) may be included. There may also be a discussion on how the above hands-on practices may be practiced and promoted in academic offices on a peer-to-peer basis.

About 3 recommended online resources on mindfulness will be shared with participants at the end (for them to take away)

Non-identifying information on the workshop host's experience with emotion regulation and mindfulness

The workshop host has researched emotion regulation with a focus on anxiety and their research interest has recently expanded to mindfulness. They have practiced mindfulness for 5+ years and have incorporated mindfulness into their previous university teaching. They also have experience teaching mindfulness in the community setting.

(429 words)

References

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